

ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE: A SERIOUS THREAT FOR ALL

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Abstract

Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR) occurs when bacteria, viruses, fungi and parasites change over time and no longer respond to medicines making infections harder to treat and increasing the risk of disease spread, severe illness and death.

As a result of drug resistance, antibiotics and other antimicrobial medicines become ineffective and infections become increasingly difficult or impossible to treat. The emergence and spread of drug-resistant pathogens that have acquired new resistance mechanisms, leading to antimicrobial resistance, continues to threaten our ability to treat common infections. Especially alarming is the rapid global spread of multi- and pan-resistant bacteria (also known as "superbugs") that cause infections that are not treatable with existing antimicrobial medicines such as antibiotics.

Keywords: Antibiotics AMR, Superbugs

Introduction**Antimicrobial resistance**

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is the ability of microorganisms to persist or grow in the presence of drugs designed to inhibit or kill them. These drugs, called antimicrobials, are used to treat infectious diseases caused by microorganisms such as bacteria, fungi, viruses and protozoan parasites.

Causes of AMR

Selective Pressure: Upon treatment with an antimicrobial, microbes are generally killed, and if, they carry resistance genes, they survive. The population of such strains increases very fast and their progenies quickly become the dominant type amongst the microbial population.

Mutation: In general, the microorganisms divide rapidly, and adapt quickly to new environmental conditions. During the division, mutations may occur, and few of them may help an individual microbe to resist the antimicrobial therapy.

Gene Transfer: Microbes that have drug-resistant genes may transfer these genes to other bacteria via several ways. Non-resistant microbes receive the new gene/s, and become resistant to antimicrobial/s. Thereafter, the resistant microbes multiply and thrive.

Inappropriate Use: Underdosing, overdosing, improper time interval between the therapeutic doses and inappropriate duration of treatment may induce AMR.

Inadequate Diagnosis: Due to incomplete or imperfect or wrong diagnosis, a clinician may prescribe a wrong antimicrobial or a broad-spectrum antimicrobial when use of a specific antimicrobial might be better. These conditions may lead to selective pressure, and in turn, it may enhance AMR.

Antimicrobials as growth promotor or as feed additive: When antimicrobials are used as growth promotor or as feed additive, there is heavy probability of development of AMR amongst the microbial pathogens present in the environment, animals and humans.

Antimicrobials as contaminants in the environment and food/feed/fodder: Currently, almost all environmental entities (water, soil etc.), food, fodder, feed etc. contaminated with antimicrobials, which causes emergence of AMR amongst the microbial pathogens present in the environment, animals and humans.

Antimicrobial groups based on mechanism of action.

Mechanism of Action	Antimicrobial Groups
Inhibit Cell Wall Synthesis	*β-Lactams
	Carbapenems
	Cephalosporins
	Monobactams
	Penicillins
	Glycopeptides
Depolarize Cell Membrane	Lipopeptides
Inhibit Protein Synthesis	*Bind to 30S Ribosomal Subunit
	Aminoglycosides
	Tetracyclines
	*Bind to 50S Ribosomal Subunit

Resistance to antibiotics occurs as a result of:

Drug inactivation,
 Drug-target modification
 Decreased intracellular accumulation associated with reduced membrane permeability (following a reduction in the expression of outer membrane-spanning porin proteins)
 Increased drug efflux
 limiting uptake of a drug
 Mutations in housekeeping-structural and regulatory genes, as well as horizontal acquisition of foreign genetic material, are some of the underlying genetic pathways involved.
 Resistance for an organism can be defined as either innate (intrinsic) or acquired (extrinsic)
Innate resistance is chromosomally encoded and relates to the general physiology of an organism arising from its existing properties such as cell wall complexity, enzymatic inactivation of an antibiotic.
Acquired resistance can arise from a mutation in a resident gene or the transfer of genetic material encoding resistance genes via plasmids, bacteriophages carrying resistance genes or transposons.
 Some bacteria have developed resistance to antibiotics that were once commonly used to treat them. For example, *Staphylococcus aureus* ('golden staph' or MRSA) and *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* (the cause of gonorrhoea) are now almost always resistant to benzyl penicillin. In the past, these infections were usually controlled by penicillin.
 The most serious concern with antibiotic resistance is that some bacteria have become resistant to almost all of the easily available antibiotics. These bacteria are able to cause serious disease and this is a major public health problem. Important examples are:
 Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA)
 Vancomycin-resistant *Enterococcus* (VRE)
 Multi-drug-resistant *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (MDR-TB)
 Carbapenem-resistant *Enterobacteriaceae* (CRE) gut bacteria
 Antimicrobial agents can be divided into groups based on the mechanism of antimicrobial activity. The main groups are: agents that inhibit cell wall synthesis, depolarize the cell membrane, inhibit protein synthesis, inhibit nucleic acid synthesis, and inhibit metabolic pathways in bacteria

	Chloramphenicol
	Lincosamides
	Macrolides
	Oxazolidinones
	Streptogramins
Inhibit Nucleic Acid Synthesis	*Quinolones
	Fluoroquinolones
Inhibit Metabolic Pathways	Sulfonamides
	Trimethoprim

Factors involved in growing resistance problem include:

Increased consumption of antimicrobial drugs, both by humans and animals

Improper prescribing of antimicrobial therapy.

Overuse of many common drugs because the choice of drug is based on a combination of low cost and low toxicity.

There may also be improper prescribing of antimicrobials drugs, such as the initial prescription of a broad-spectrum drug that is unnecessary, or ultimately found to be ineffective for the organism(s) causing the infection. The danger is that excessive use of antibiotics in humans leads to emergence of resistant organisms. In addition, prior use of antimicrobial drugs puts a patient at risk for infection with a drug resistant organism, and those patients with the highest exposure to antimicrobials are most often those who are infected with resistant bacteria.

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